

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ISSUE 5

 Acceptance of papers **May, 2026**

Acceptance of papers
Published monthly

Topics
economics,
technology, social
sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR FORMING AND IMPLEMENTING INVESTMENT POLICY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS... 8 Abduvaliyev Sanjar Abdurahmanovich	8
EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BASED ON BUDGETING IN ENERGY ENTERPRISES (A FACTOR ANALYSIS CASE OF "HUDUDGAZTA'MINOT" JSC)..... 17 Sobirov Shoyadbek Kurbonaliyevich	17
PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION23 Mamatkulov Gulom Rustamovich	23
OPTIMIZING THE BALANCE BETWEEN LIQUIDITY AND CREDIT RISKS IN ENSURING BANKING STABILITY 30 Anvarov Asliddin Nabijon ugli	30
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....34 Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi, Dilshod Anvarjonovich Ismailov	34
MODERN TRENDS AND EFFICIENCY OF LENDING TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN..39 Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	39
ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND CRIME (CASE OF UZBEKISTAN) 42 Khusniddinova Gulnoza	42
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN'S FINANCIAL SYSTEM 47 Qobilova Nodira Qayumjon qizi, Normurodov Kh.E.	47
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN 52 Mamadzhanova Tuygunoy Akhmadzhanovna	52
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY56 Otbosarov Abrorbek Adhamjon o'g'li	56
LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX (LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX) MODEL IN POWER GRID ENTERPRISES.. 61 Khojimurodov Zukhriddin Shukurullo oglu	61
MICROPROJECTS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY AND LITERACY OF THE POPULATION 67 Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	67
INSTITUTIONAL VA TEXNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA INNOVATION BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..... 74 Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	74
PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL CLUSTERS IN THE LIGHT INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN 80 Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadinovich	80
DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM GLOBAL TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES.....84 Sabitov Oybek Abduganievich, Sattoriy Fayzullokh Abdijabbor ugli	84
PROPERTIES OF HEAVY CONCRETE DISPERSEDLY REINFORCED WITH NON-METALLIC FIBERS AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CALCULATING CONCRETE STRUCTURES BASED ON THEM 90 Usmonova Durdona, Gulomova Dilnura	90
THE EFFECT OF STABLE AND DYNAMIC PRICING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR 98 Anvar DEBERDIYEV	98
ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.. 102 M.O. Yo'ldoshova	102

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	106
Rasulev Bobirjon Atkhamovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR REGULATING NON-STANDARD EMPLOYMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES	110
Fayzullayev Nurulla Bakhromovich	
PRIORITIES FOR IMPROVING THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	117
Gulira'no Atabekovna Ruzmetova	
FACTORS AFFECTING TAX PAYMENT SYSTEMS, EXISTING PROBLEMS, AND THEIR CAUSES	124
Tangirqulov Gulom Baxtiyorovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES IN REDUCING CARBON EMISSIONS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ECONOMETRIC APPROACH.....	129
Kuziboev Bekhzod Hamidovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE SILK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	134
Bahriddinov Asror Rakhmatovich, Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
STATE OF LENDING TO SMALL BUSINESS PROJECTS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	138
Nargiza Norqobilova Abdiqodirovna	
CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	143
Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi	
ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN NON-STATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS .	148
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
THE NATURE AND ESSENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES IN MASS MEDIA ORGANIZATIONS.....	151
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF ALGORITHMS FOR RECOVERING MISSING (NAN) VALUES IN INFORMATION SYSTEM DATA	156
Yarmatov Sherzodjon Shokir oglu, Orifov Oxunjon Fazliddinzoda	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES	167
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
IMPROVING LOAN PORTFOLIO QUALITY AND CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS	173
Turgunov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
INNOVATION CAPABILITIES AND EXPORT PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF SUPPLY CHAIN INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION — EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	177
Mukhammadyaminova Shakhzoda	
URBAN PLANNING OF TRANSPORT INTERCHANGE HUBS NEAR TUBERCULOSIS CARE FACILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN	183
Gabibova Irina Vagifovna, Abdumuminova Diyora Gayratovna	
ADAPTING INTERNAL AUDIT STANDARDS IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS TO PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PRACTICES.....	192
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
ECONOMETRIC EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN KHOREZM REGION	197
Otajanov Umid Abdullayevich	
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN RECLAMATION AND GIS TECHNOLOGIES ON SALINE SOILS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN.....	205
Tajibaev Berdakh	
ISSUES REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE “TOLLING OPERATIONS” MODULE IN THE GOODS MOVEMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UNDER THE CUSTOMS TERRITORY PROCESSING REGIME	212
Lutpullaev Shukrullo Kudratullaevich	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN ENHANCING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN	218
Akmaljon Odilov	
INTERNATIONAL TRENDS OF DIGITALIZATION IN CUSTOMS MANAGEMENT	222
Radjapova Latofat Sardarovna	
THE ROLE OF TAX POLICY IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY	230
Dexkanova Shodiyona Kaxramon qizi	
PRACTICES IN ENTERPRISE COST STRUCTURE MANAGEMENT AND DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	236
Aymukhammedova Amina Kakajanovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	242
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
RECONCEPTUALIZING BUSINESS INCUBATORS IN STARTUP ECOSYSTEMS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS	246
Gafujon Usmanov	
DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN MARKETING APPROACHES TO CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES	257
Safarov Bakhtiyor Djurakulovich	
MECHANISMS FOR EVALUATING AND IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE PUBLIC TRANSPORT SECTOR	263
Berdiyorov Temur Azamatovich	
THE INFLUENCE OF HYDRODYNAMIC ASPECTS OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL RISE ON URBAN WATERLOGGING	268
B.D. Abdullaev, B.R. Nasibov, Sh.T. Irgashev, D. Abdullaev	
BASIC INFORMATION MODEL OF A DIGITAL OBJECT	277
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich, Karakhanova Alsu Muratalievna, Keldiyorov Sirojiddin Tura ugli, Zayniddinova Zebiniso Akmalovna	
COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE AND TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SOLAR PANEL MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS	281
Urishev Omadjon, Kushakova Sarvinoz, Kamolboyev Sirojbek	
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR FORMING ECOLOGICALLY ORIENTED MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	294
Kholov Hamza Tajiddinovich	
INVESTIGATION OF GERMANIUM EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGY FROM TECHNOGENIC METALLURGICAL WASTE	301
Yormatov Dostonbek, Shodiyev Abbos, Muhammadiyev Elbek	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND OPTIMIZING PRODUCTION COSTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY	309
Utbasarov Doniyorjon Bakhtiyarovich	
THEORETICAL, PRACTICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF AUDITING THE ACTIVITIES OF ECONOMIC ENTITIES ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS	318
Mirzaeva Sabina Khushnudovna, Khaydarova Dildora Djakhongirovna	
THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON WOMEN'S LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF UZBEKISTAN UNDER INDUSTRY 4.0	322
Doniyorova Zukhrabonu Alisher qizi	
LEVEL OF ENSURING FOOD SECURITY: IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISMS AND INSTRUMENTS	328
Sodiqjon Qodirovich Mattiyev	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY, AND LOCALIZATION POLICY OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT SYSTEM	334
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH VOSITASIDA	339
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	

PROJECT-ORIENTED ESP32 IOT CURRICULUM WITH A SHARED-RESOURCE LABORATORY MODEL: DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION, AND LESSONS LEARNED	344
Ulugbek Tursunaliyev, Lazizbek Yusupov	
FIVE-CRITERION METHODOLOGY OF INTERNAL CONTROL ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	353
Babakulova Matluba Kurbannazarovna	
THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION-INDUSTRY INTEGRATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY.....	357
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
MECHANISMS AND DIRECTIONS FOR DEEPENING REGIONAL INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	361
Akbarova Kamola Akmaljonovna	
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN HEALTHCARE INSTITUTIONS	368
Saidov Suhrob Shodmonovich	
IMPROVING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN'S SERVICE SECTOR: BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.....	371
Shermatov Axror Abdixakimovich	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING CUSTOMS RISK PROFILE INDICATORS BASED ON MATHEMATICAL AND STATISTICAL METHODS	377
Niyazov Sherzod Shovkat ugli	
AN INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK FOR CRYPTO-ASSET REGULATION: ADDRESSING LEGAL UNCERTAINTY IN DIGITAL FINANCIAL SYSTEMS	385
Iminokhunov Abdukokhor A., Khakimov Abdurakhmon Mukhammad-Ali ugli	
THEORETICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE SERVICE SECTOR	396
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
REGIONAL ASSESSMENT OF THE OPENNESS OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON A SYNTHETIC INDICATOR.....	401
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE REGIONAL INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND INDICATORS SYSTEM.....	407
Maxmudov Jasurbek Ergashevich	
ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT ATTRACTION PRACTICES IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	412
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli	
ASSESSMENT OF SOURCES OF EQUITY FORMATION IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THEIR USE.....	421
Savinova Galina Anatolevna	
DIGITAL MARKETING INTEGRATION, KPI ARCHITECTURE AND CAUSAL EVALUATION OF ENTERPRISE COMPETITIVENESS IN EMERGING MARKETS: A CONCEPTUAL-METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR UZBEKISTAN	429
Bakhtiyor Ruziev Eshmuminovich	
IMPROVING FOREIGN EXCHANGE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN	434
B.K. Tugalov	
CHANGES IN THE BIOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF HOOFED ANIMALS IN THE TUGAI FORESTS OF THE SOUTHERN ARAL REGION UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS.....	438
J. U. Tilepov, A. A. Jumamuratova	
ECONOMETRIC ASSESSMENT MECHANISMS OF THE IMPACT OF TRADE SERVICE QUALITY INDICATORS ON THE LEVEL OF COMPETITIVENESS	442
Toxirov Javlon Raximovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BIZNES MUHITINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI ..	447
Xazratov Abror Panjiyevich, Muratkulov Xumoyun Dilshodovich	

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COTTON PROCESSING INDUSTRY IN BUSINESS ENTITIES	452
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li, Sayitbayev Shermirza Datkamirzayevich	
BALANCING ECONOMIC GROWTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN TOURISM	456
Kamalova Malika Umidjanovna, Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL FOR IMPROVING FACE-ID TECHNOLOGY IN ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY ON E-PLATFORMS.....	462
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
SOLIQLAR VA DAVLAT BUDJETI: SOLIQ TIZIMINING BUDJETIGA TA'SIRI	467
Izbosarov Bobur Baxriddinovich, Umirov Sherzod Baxriddinovich	
СИСТЕМНЫЕ ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ БАНКОВСКОГО СЕКТОРА УЗБЕКИСТАНА	472
Аширкулов Диорбек Алишер угли, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	
THE IMPACT OF INFLATION ON THE ECONOMY AND WAYS TO REDUCE IT	479
Abdullaeva Zulfiya Izzatovna, Ashurova Jasmina Jora qizi	
КОЛЛИЗИИ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО И СЕМЕЙНОГО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВА В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СУПРУГОВ.....	483
Рашидова Зилола Жавлонбековна	
SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES (SME) AND DISTRICT-LEVEL PANEL DATA ANALYSIS IN THE CONTEXT OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	487
Ismoilov Elyorjon Makhamadali ugli, Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND ONLINE PLATFORMS IN THE TOURISM SECTOR	495
Bakayev Ziyovuddinxon Toshbolta o'g'li	
CHINA'S DIGITAL YUAN (E-CNY) PROJECT: ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT, PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE, AND POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN	500
Tashquziyev Suxrob Abdurazzak ugli	
VALYUTA KURSI REJIMLARI (ERKIN SUZUVCHI, BOG'LANGAN, ARALASH): MILLIY VALYUTA BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRINI NAZARIY SOLISHTIRISH	505
G'afurov Olimjon G'olib o'g'li	
IMPACT OF DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN, STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND TRENDS	510
Ibodullayev Navro'zbek Ikram o'g'li, Akbarov Nodir G'ofurovich	
THE IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE-ORIENTED FISCAL POLICY ON REGIONAL COMPETITIVENESS. 517	
Ne'matov Ne'matulla Erkinboyevich	

THE IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE-ORIENTED FISCAL POLICY ON REGIONAL COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract. This thesis examines the role of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy in strengthening regional competitiveness and promoting balanced socio-economic development. The study analyzes the theoretical foundations of infrastructure investment within the framework of regional development theories, fiscal decentralization, and New Economic Geography. Particular attention is given to the relationship between public infrastructure expenditures, investment attractiveness, business activity, and territorial integration. The research highlights that transport, energy, logistics, and communication infrastructure significantly influence regional productivity and economic concentration. The case of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan is used to evaluate the practical importance of infrastructure-oriented fiscal mechanisms under environmentally and economically constrained conditions. The findings indicate that targeted infrastructure spending contributes to investment growth, employment generation, and improved regional competitiveness. At the same time, inefficient allocation of public resources and institutional weaknesses may reduce the effectiveness of fiscal policy. The study concludes that differentiated infrastructure policy, combined with fiscal sustainability and institutional modernization, is essential for achieving long-term regional development.

Keywords: Infrastructure policy, fiscal mechanisms, regional competitiveness, fiscal decentralization, territorial development, public investment, regional inequality, New Economic Geography, Karakalpakstan, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Infratuzilmaga yo'naltirilgan fiskal siyosatning hududiy raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish hamda muvozanatli ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ta'minlashdagi o'rni tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotda infratuzilma investitsiyalarining nazariy asoslari hududiy rivojlanish nazariyalari, fiskal markazsizlashtirish va Yangi iqtisodiy geografiya konsepsiyalari doirasida tahlil qilingan. Davlatning infratuzilmaga yo'naltirilgan xarajatlari, investitsion jozibadorlik, tadbirkorlik faolligi va hududlararo integratsiya o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikka alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Transport, energetika, logistika va kommunikatsiya infratuzilmasining hududiy unumdorlik hamda iqtisodiy faollikning hududiy konsentratsiyasiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi asoslab berilgan. O'zbekiston va Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi misolida ekologik hamda iqtisodiy cheklovlar sharoitida infratuzilmaga yo'naltirilgan fiskal mexanizmlarning amaliy ahamiyati baholangan. Natijalar maqsadli infratuzilma xarajatlari investitsiyalar hajmining oshishi, yangi ish o'rinlarining yaratilishi va hududiy raqobatbardoshlikning kuchayishiga xizmat qilishini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, davlat resurslarining samarasiz taqsimlanishi hamda institutsional cheklovlar fiskal siyosat samaradorligini pasaytirishi mumkinligi aniqlangan. Uzoq muddatli hududiy rivojlanishni ta'minlash uchun differensial infratuzilma siyosatini fiskal barqarorlik va institutsional modernizatsiya bilan uyg'unlashtirish zarurligi xulosa qilingan.

Kalits o'zlar: infratuzilma siyosati, fiskal mexanizmlar, hududiy raqobatbardoshlik, fiskal markazsizlashtirish, hududiy rivojlanish, davlat investitsiyalari, hududlararo tengsizlik, Yangi iqtisodiy geografiya, Qoraqalpog'iston, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. Исследована роль инфраструктурно-ориентированной фискальной политики в повышении региональной конкурентоспособности и обеспечении сбалансированного социально-экономического развития. Теоретические основы инфраструктурных инвестиций рассмотрены в контексте теорий регионального развития, фискальной децентрализации и Новой экономической географии. Особое внимание уделено взаимосвязи между государственными расходами на инфраструктуру,

инвестиционной привлекательностью, предпринимательской активностью и территориальной интеграцией. Обосновано существенное влияние транспортной, энергетической, логистической и коммуникационной инфраструктуры на региональную производительность и пространственную концентрацию экономической деятельности. На примере Узбекистана и Республики Каракалпакстан дана оценка практической значимости инфраструктурно-ориентированных фискальных механизмов в условиях экологических и экономических ограничений. Результаты исследования показывают, что целевые инфраструктурные расходы способствуют росту инвестиций, созданию новых рабочих мест и укреплению региональной конкурентоспособности. Вместе с тем неэффективное распределение государственных ресурсов и институциональные ограничения могут снижать результативность фискальной политики. Сделан вывод о необходимости сочетания дифференцированной инфраструктурной политики с обеспечением фискальной устойчивости и институциональной модернизацией для достижения долгосрочного регионального развития.

Ключевые слова: инфраструктурная политика, фискальные механизмы, региональная конкурентоспособность, фискальная децентрализация, территориальное развитие, государственные инвестиции, региональное неравенство, Новая экономическая география, Каракалпакстан, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy has become one of the key instruments of regional economic development in modern economies. In both developed and developing countries, public investment directed toward transport, energy, communication, and logistics infrastructure plays a crucial role in strengthening territorial competitiveness and reducing regional disparities. Infrastructure not only improves production efficiency and market accessibility but also stimulates investment activity, employment growth, and regional integration.

In the context of globalization and increasing economic competition, regions with developed infrastructure systems demonstrate stronger competitiveness and higher investment attractiveness. Conversely, territories with weak transport connectivity, insufficient energy supply, and underdeveloped public services often experience lower economic dynamism and limited private sector activity. Therefore, infrastructure development has become a strategic priority of fiscal policy in many countries.

The issue is particularly important for transition economies such as Uzbekistan, where ongoing economic reforms have created new opportunities for reducing territorial disparities and promoting more balanced regional development. Recent government programs aimed at modernizing transport systems, expanding energy infrastructure, improving water supply networks, and developing digital communications have increased the role of infrastructure expenditures in regional policy. Special attention has been given to environmentally vulnerable territories such as the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Theoretical approaches to infrastructure and regional competitiveness have evolved within the framework of regional development theories and New Economic Geography. Perroux emphasized the importance of growth poles and infrastructure concentration in stimulating regional development. Myrdal explained how infrastructure inequality contributes to cumulative territorial disparities. Krugman later demonstrated that transport costs, agglomeration effects, and market accessibility significantly influence regional competitiveness and spatial concentration of economic activity.

Infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy is also closely connected with fiscal decentralization and public investment management. Modern economic literature highlights that effective infrastructure spending improves:

- regional accessibility;
- business activity;
- labor mobility;
- industrial diversification;
- territorial integration.

At the same time, inefficient allocation of public resources, weak institutional quality, and poor project selection may reduce the effectiveness of fiscal expenditures and increase fiscal risks.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan represents a unique case for analyzing infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy due to its environmental vulnerability, geographical remoteness, and infrastructural limitations. Improving transport, water, energy, and communication systems in the region remains one of the essential conditions for strengthening socio-economic resilience and regional competitiveness.

The main purpose of this thesis is to examine the impact of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy on regional competitiveness and to evaluate its importance for regional development in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship between infrastructure development and regional competitiveness has long been discussed in regional economics and public finance literature. Modern economic theories emphasize that infrastructure is not only a supporting component of economic activity but also one of the key determinants of long-term regional growth and territorial integration.

One of the earliest theoretical approaches related to infrastructure and regional development was introduced by François Perroux (1955) through the concept of growth poles. According to Perroux, economic growth emerges around strategically important territories characterized by industrial concentration, infrastructure availability, and investment activity. Infrastructure serves as a catalyst that attracts:

- capital;
- labor resources;
- industrial enterprises;
- innovation activity.

This theory explains why infrastructure-oriented fiscal expenditures are often concentrated in economically strategic regions.

Albert Hirschman (1958) further developed this idea through the theory of unbalanced growth. Hirschman argued that limited public resources should be directed toward sectors and territories capable of generating strong multiplier effects. According to the author, infrastructure investment creates forward and backward linkages that stimulate broader economic activity. In this context, transport systems, energy supply, and logistics infrastructure become essential drivers of regional transformation.

Gunnar Myrdal (1957) analyzed regional inequality through the theory of cumulative causation. He emphasized that regions with developed infrastructure continuously attract more investment and skilled labor, while peripheral territories lose economic resources over time. Myrdal referred to this process as “backwash effects.” Therefore, state intervention through infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy becomes necessary to reduce territorial disparities and support vulnerable regions.

A major contribution to regional competitiveness theory was made by Paul Krugman (1991) through New Economic Geography (NEG). Krugman demonstrated that:

- transportation costs;
- economies of scale;
- market accessibility;
- agglomeration effects directly influence spatial economic concentration. According to this approach, regions with better infrastructure achieve stronger competitiveness because firms tend to locate where logistics costs are lower and market access is greater.

Krugman’s theory is highly relevant for developing economies where infrastructural inequality remains one of the main barriers to balanced regional development. In countries such as Uzbekistan, infrastructure accessibility significantly influences investment concentration and industrial activity.

Fiscal decentralization literature also emphasizes the importance of infrastructure expenditures in territorial development. Oates (1972) argued that local governments can allocate infrastructure resources more efficiently because they possess better information about regional needs and priorities. According to the fiscal federalism approach, stronger local fiscal autonomy improves:

- infrastructure quality;
- public service delivery;
- regional investment attractiveness.

Rodríguez-Pose and Ezcurra (2010) examined the relationship between decentralization and regional disparities. Their findings suggest that infrastructure investment becomes more effective when supported by strong institutional quality and local governance capacity. The authors also emphasize that poorly coordinated fiscal decentralization may increase territorial inequality if weaker regions lack sufficient financial resources.

Lessmann (2009) analyzed the connection between fiscal decentralization and regional inequality using cross-country empirical evidence. The study concluded that infrastructure-oriented public expenditures reduce regional disparities more effectively in countries with developed institutional systems and transparent fiscal governance.

Infrastructure policy is particularly important for environmentally vulnerable regions such as Karakalpakstan. Due to geographical remoteness, ecological constraints, and limited industrial diversification, the region experiences weaker market integration and lower investment attractiveness. Therefore, infrastructure modernization represents one of the key conditions for improving territorial competitiveness and socio-economic resilience.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy plays a strategic role in

regional development. Modern regional theories consistently emphasize that effective infrastructure investment strengthens territorial integration, stimulates economic activity, and improves regional competitiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies qualitative research methods to examine the impact of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy on regional competitiveness. The methodological framework is based on regional development theory, fiscal decentralization, and New Economic Geography.

The research employs systematic literature review, comparative analysis, and institutional analysis to evaluate the relationship between infrastructure investment and regional development. Scientific works of Perroux, Hirschman, Myrdal, Krugman, and Oates serve as the theoretical foundation of the study.

Descriptive analysis is used to assess the effects of infrastructure expenditures on investment attractiveness, business activity, employment, and territorial integration. The study relies on secondary data obtained from official reports of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of Uzbekistan, the Statistics Agency of Uzbekistan, OECD, and UNDP.

In addition, a case study approach is applied to analyze the Republic of Karakalpakstan as a region undergoing environmental and infrastructure transformation processes. This allows the evaluation of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy in enhancing regional competitiveness and strengthening socio-economic resilience

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings of the study indicate that infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy significantly influences regional competitiveness and territorial economic sustainability. Public expenditures directed toward transport systems, energy infrastructure, communication networks, and water supply improve regional accessibility and create favorable conditions for investment activity.

In Uzbekistan, large-scale infrastructure reforms implemented in recent years have strengthened territorial integration and accelerated regional economic transformation. Government investments in:

- road modernization;
- railway connectivity;
- energy supply systems;
- digital infrastructure;
- logistics networks have contributed to improving business conditions and increasing regional competitiveness.

The results show that regions with stronger infrastructure systems demonstrate:

- higher industrial activity;
- stronger investment inflows;
- better labor market conditions;
- greater business density.

These observations are consistent with Krugman's New Economic Geography theory, which emphasizes that lower transport costs and stronger market accessibility stimulate economic concentration and regional competitiveness.

The case of Karakalpakstan clearly demonstrates the strategic importance of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy. Due to geographical remoteness and environmental vulnerability, the region faces several infrastructural constraints, including:

- weak logistics connectivity;
- limited industrial infrastructure;
- insufficient water systems;
- energy supply limitations.

These factors reduce private investment attractiveness and limit regional economic diversification.

At the same time, recent infrastructure-oriented fiscal expenditures directed toward:

- transport modernization;
- water infrastructure projects;
- renewable energy systems;
- digital communication expansion have partially improved territorial accessibility and socio-economic stability in the region.

The analysis also reveals that infrastructure expenditures generate strong multiplier effects. Infrastructure development stimulates:

- construction activity;
- employment growth;
- SME development;
- service sector expansion;
- regional trade integration.

This process strengthens endogenous regional growth capacity and improves territorial resilience.

However, the effectiveness of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy depends not only on the volume of public expenditures but also on institutional quality and project selection efficiency. In some cases, poorly coordinated infrastructure projects may lead to:

- inefficient resource allocation;
- fiscal pressure;
- low economic returns;
- unfinished investment projects.

Therefore, infrastructure spending should be based on:

- cost-benefit analysis;
- regional competitiveness indicators;
- long-term territorial development strategies;
- transparent fiscal governance mechanisms.

Fiscal decentralization also plays an important role in infrastructure policy effectiveness. Local governments are often better positioned to identify regional infrastructure priorities and allocate resources according to territorial needs. Nevertheless, insufficient local fiscal capacity may weaken infrastructure financing potential in economically vulnerable regions.

The study confirms that infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy is one of the most important instruments for reducing regional disparities and improving territorial competitiveness in Uzbekistan. Particularly for Karakalpakstan, sustainable infrastructure modernization remains essential for strengthening socio-economic resilience and attracting long-term investment activity.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study demonstrates that infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy plays a decisive role in strengthening regional competitiveness and ensuring balanced territorial development. Public investments directed toward transport, energy, communication, and water infrastructure significantly improve regional accessibility, investment attractiveness, and business activity.

Theoretical approaches developed by Perroux, Hirschman, Myrdal, and Krugman confirm that infrastructure represents one of the key drivers of regional economic concentration and territorial integration. Regions with developed infrastructure systems are more capable of attracting investment, expanding industrial activity, and improving labor market conditions.

The analysis of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan indicates that infrastructure modernization contributes positively to:

- employment growth;
- SME development;
- investment inflows;
- regional economic resilience.

At the same time, infrastructural disparities between central and peripheral territories remain substantial. Particularly in Karakalpakstan, geographical remoteness, ecological challenges, and limited industrial diversification continue to weaken regional competitiveness.

The findings also reveal that the effectiveness of infrastructure-oriented fiscal policy depends on:

- institutional quality;
- transparent fiscal governance;
- efficient project selection;
- long-term territorial planning.

Without proper coordination and economic justification, large-scale infrastructure expenditures may reduce fiscal efficiency and increase budgetary pressure.

Furthermore, fiscal decentralization improves infrastructure policy effectiveness when local governments possess sufficient financial and institutional capacity. Stronger local participation in infrastructure planning allows territorial priorities to be addressed more accurately and efficiently.

Overall, the study concludes that sustainable regional competitiveness in Uzbekistan requires:

- differentiated infrastructure policy;

- stronger infrastructure-oriented public investment;
- improved fiscal decentralization mechanisms;
- institutional modernization;
- enhanced regional investment attractiveness.

For environmentally vulnerable territories such as Karakalpakstan, infrastructure modernization should remain one of the central priorities of regional fiscal policy and long-term socio-economic development strategy.

References

1. Hirschman, A.O. (1958) *The Strategy of Economic Development*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
2. Krugman, P. (1991) 'Increasing returns and economic geography', *Journal of Political Economy*, 99(3), pp. 483–499.
3. Lessmann, C. (2009) 'Fiscal decentralization and regional disparity: Evidence from cross-section and panel data', *Dresden Discussion Paper Series in Economics*, No. 08/09, pp. 1–36.
4. Myrdal, G. (1957) *Economic Theory and Underdeveloped Regions*. London: Duckworth.
5. Oates, W.E. (1972) *Fiscal Federalism*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
6. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2016) *Fiscal Decentralisation and Regional Disparities*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
7. Perroux, F. (1955) 'Note sur la notion de pôle de croissance', *Économie Appliquée*, 8, pp. 307–320.
8. Rodríguez-Pose, A. and Ezcurra, R. (2010) 'Does decentralization matter for regional disparities? A cross-country analysis', *Journal of Economic Geography*, 10(5), pp. 619–644.
9. Romer, P.M. (1990) 'Endogenous technological change', *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), pp. S71–S102.
10. Statistics Agency of Uzbekistan (2024) *Regional Statistical Bulletin of Uzbekistan*. Tashkent: Statistics Agency.
11. UNDP (2023) *Regional Human Development Report for Uzbekistan*. New York: United Nations Development Programme.
12. Uzbekistan Ministry of Economy and Finance (2024) *Regional Budget and Fiscal Policy Report*. Tashkent: Ministry of Economy and Finance.
13. Williamson, J.G. (1965) 'Regional inequality and the process of national development', *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 13(4), pp. 1–84.
14. Yusupov, A. and Kallibekova, D. (2022) 'Regional competitiveness and territorial differentiation in Karakalpakstan', *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 1(1), pp. 22–35.
15. Zokirov, S. (2024) *Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot*. Tashkent: Turon Publishing.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 5

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